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A STUDY ON LEADERSHIP COMMUNICATION STYLES: A DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF HEALTH CARE PROFESSIONALS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DHIRAJ HOSPITAL

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Abstract

For health care organizations and professionals to improve their performance in critical events, team dynamics must be understood better, and strategies for more effective communication must be described. It is these differences that suggest an analysis of leadership and motivation can result in general conclusions about behavior and performance. The present research was qualitative in nature. It was both questionnaires based and observational in nature. We conducted this study in Dhiraj General Hospital. We interacted with healthcare staff of Dhiraj Hospital, Pipariya. Through the observation process and questionnaire, I was able to explore twelve different health care professionals' perspectives of leadership. The managers scored the highest rating. From this research, the critical need for these health care leaders to engage in self-reflection to better understand themselves and have "thinking time" to set the direction for the future of their organization is evident. The health of each organization depends upon the health of the leader and his or her greater understanding of self. Future research needs to look at the core coursework of nurses, physicians, and administrators in educating them on the principles of leadership and effective communication.

KEY WORDS: Leadership style, leaders, hospital

Introduction

Understanding leadership in profession like healthcare is very important because very critical incidents arise. For health care organizations and professionals to improve their performance in critical events, team dynamics must be understood better, and strategies for more effective communication must be described. Although inter-professional teams consist of individuals who are expert in their respective disciplines, they do not always bring effective inter-professional skills to the team. A “team of experts” is not necessarily an “expert team.”

We are like some other people in that we have similar personality traits which cause us to be more dominant and aggressive, while others may be more passive and submissive. Finally, we are unique in that no other person has the same genetic make-up, past experiences, or view of the world. It is these differences that suggest an analysis of leadership and motivation can result in general conclusions about behavior and performance. In many circles, there is continuous debate about whether leaders are born or developed.

Leadership is the influence that particular individuals exert upon the goal achievement of others in an organizational context. An earlier unit on Board Governance addresses in a limited way, the impacts of leaders on performance. We stated that leaders have an ability to see how different aspects of a situation fit together and influence each other. They seek out alliances, opportunities, and approach goals in a proactive way. They have a positive effect on others, which attracts support from those who have similar needs for accomplishment. Their self confidence creates a belief in other people’s abilities; therefore, emphasis is placed on empowerment and freedom.

Types of leadership are ^[1]

1. The pacesetter leader expects and models excellence and self-direction. If this style were summed up in one phrase, it would be “Do as I do, now.” The pacesetter style works best when the team is already motivated and skilled, and the leader needs quick results. Used extensively, however, this style can overwhelm team members and squelch innovation.
2. The authoritative leader mobilizes the team toward a common vision and focuses on end goals, leaving the means up to each individual. If this style were summed up in one phrase, it would be “Come with me.” The authoritative style works best when the team needs a new vision because circumstances have changed, or when explicit guidance is not required. Authoritative leaders inspire an entrepreneurial spirit and vibrant enthusiasm for the mission. It is not the best fit when the leader is working with a team of experts who know more than him or her.
3. The affiliative leader works to create emotional bonds that bring a feeling of bonding and belonging to the organization. If this style were summed up in one phrase, it would be “People come first.” The affiliative style works best in times of stress, when teammates need to heal from a trauma, or when the team needs to rebuild trust. This style should not be used exclusively, because a sole reliance on praise and nurturing can foster mediocre performance and a lack of direction.
4. The coaching leader develops people for the future. If this style were summed up in one phrase, it would be “Try this.” The coaching style works best when the leader wants to help teammates build lasting personal strengths that make them more successful overall. It is least effective when teammates are defiant and unwilling to change or learn, or if the leader lacks proficiency.
5. The coercive leader demands immediate compliance. If this style were summed up in one phrase, it would be “Do what I tell you.” The coercive style is most effective in times of crisis, such as in a company turnaround or a takeover attempt, or during an actual emergency like a tornado or a fire. This style can also help control a problem teammate when everything else has failed. However, it should be avoided in almost every other case because it can alienate people and stifle flexibility and inventiveness.
6. The democratic leader builds consensus through participation. If this style were summed up in one phrase, it would be “What do you think?” The democratic style is most effective when the leader needs the team to buy into or have ownership of a decision, plan, or goal, or if he or she is uncertain and needs fresh ideas from qualified teammates. It is not the best choice in an emergency situation, when time is of

the essence for another reason or when teammates are not informed enough to offer sufficient guidance to the leader.

Literature Review

Rebekah Roger^[2] (May 2006) the study of leadership in health care is carried out for many reasons. Health care leaders will inevitably have an impact on the lives of many people, as individuals rely on physicians and nurses during some of the most critical moments in their lives. Methodology used is the interpretive and critical paradigms. Second, he described the process of conducting the in-depth interviews that were used in the study. Third, he described the participants and the recruitment process. Finally, he addressed the methods of data collection, which included in-depth interviews and document analysis. Through the interview process, he was able to explore twelve different health care professionals' perspectives of leadership. From thoroughly reviewing the transcriptions, it was clear that there were many themes that were present in all three groups. The three most evident themes were viewpoints on leadership, decision making, and relationships. The practical implications of this research are important for all health care professionals. It is evident that physician's nurses, and administrators must have an increased awareness of self and individual leadership style. In addition, it is important for each of these health care leaders to be engaged in practices of reflection. Bar-On defines self-reflection as "a process of exploring and evaluating our thoughts, feelings, and behavior."

Kevin Duncan^[3] (June 2009) The primary focus of This research paper was to examine two main objective of this section of my research paper will be to evaluate the different styles of leader as of management – leadership and communication as it applies in the municipal setting. Although the theories of leadership will mainly focus on the municipal management sector; they are certainly applicable to all workplaces. The initial examination of this topic began with the review of materials. A number of websites were also found to contain useful articles and research on the subject of leadership and communication. The links provided on these websites provided additional relevant information and further areas of research addition to the aforementioned areas of research, surveys Situational Leadership Styles. Leaders. However the concept of leadership has been written about and studied since ancient times. This paper will key in on the main type of leadership that is most often used by municipal managers. Due to the diversity of the work force and the general public at large managers must be flexible and adaptable, depending on any given situation. Therefore the type of leadership most used by municipal managers might possibly be situational. As research paper has shown by focusing on the basics of leadership and communication municipal managers can improve those skills which are vital in workplace harmony and morale. By focusing on the tools necessary to effectively be a leader to individuals, managers can gain the respect and trust of their employees. Managers must skillfully lead by example.

Paul E. MadloK^[4] (October 2009) the purpose of the current study was to examine the influence of supervisor task leadership style, relational leadership style, and communicate or competence on employee job and communication satisfaction. Participants were 220: working adults (52.7% male, $n = 116$; and 47.3%female, $n = 104$), with a range in tenure from 1 to 40 years ($M = 8.6$, $SD = 10.0$). Of the participants, 112 reported working for a female supervisor and 108 reported working for a male supervisor. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 64 ($M = 34.5$, $SD = 14$), whereas supervisors' ages ranged from 22 to 75 ($M = 42.6$, $SD = 10.7$). Participants reported working for a variety of organization including education (7.0%), government (15.0%), service (47.3%), high tech (7.1%), manufacturing (14.9%), civil service (4.2%), and other (4.5%). The first hypothesis predicted significant and positive relationships between Supervisor communication competence and employee job and communication Satisfaction. The second hypothesis predicted significant and positive relationships between supervisor relational leadership style and employee job and communication Satisfaction.

PARAMETERS
Leadership characteristics
Response of others to your decision
Delivery of information
Effect of superior's decision
Team work

Methodology

The present research was qualitative in nature. It was both questionnaires based and observational in nature. The questionnaires were open ended in nature. One purpose of this research was to provide a descriptive analysis of the leadership styles observed among health care professionals. We were most interested in learning about the similarities and differences that exist among the leadership styles of physicians, nurses, and administrators. We were also interested in determining whether there is certain leadership traits that make them better suited for their field. In order to achieve these goals, we drew on the interpretive and critical paradigms of research.

We conducted this study in Dhiraj General Hospital. We interacted with healthcare staff of Dhiraj Hospital, Pipariya. We had observed the behavior of the professionals for 2 and half months but the leadership styles were observed for 15 days.

The observation was based on following parameters as in Table 1.

These parameters were scored on a 4 point scale ranging from 1: Average, 2: Good, 3: Very Good and 4: Excellent.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. The person who administrates the hospital and leads.
2. The doctors who lead others.
3. The head nurses as they are the main and many people work under them.

It was distributed to resident doctors, head nurses and administrators at Dhiraj Hospital.

The questionnaires that were fully filled were accepted and the rest were not included in the study. The acceptance rate of questionnaire was 80% and rest 20% Questionnaires were not returned.

Analysis

Through the observation process and questionnaire, I was able to explore twelve different health care professionals' perspectives of leadership.

Table 2 shows the evaluation of various professionals on the parameters in designations on a 4 point scale ranging from 1: Average, 2: Good, 3: Very Good and 4: Excellent.

	Leadership characteristics	Response of others to your decision	Delivery of information	Effect of superior's decision	Team work	TOTAL SCORE out of 20
Nurse 1	3	2	3	1	3	12
Nurse 2	1	2	1	2	1	7
Nurse 3	3	2	3	3	2	13
Nurse 4	2	2	3	2	2	11
Administrator	3	4	4	1	3	15
Chief Floor Manager	3	3	4	3	1	14
Floor Manager-1	4	4	4	3	3	18
Floor Manager-2	2	3	3	4	4	16
Floor Manager-3	4	4	4	2	4	18
Doctor 1	2	3	2	3	4	14
Doctor 2	1	1	2	2	2	8
Doctor 3	2	3	3	3	4	15

It can be seen from table 2, that the managers scored the highest rating. They scored highest in all the parameters. It can also be observed that the chief floor manager and few of the nursing staff was found to be low scorer on the parameter related to team work. Nursing staff were found to have low score in the following parameters that were evaluated like leadership, delivery of information, team work and effect of superior's decision. One of the doctors was found to score low in leadership characteristics and their response if someone disagrees with their decision.

Hospital administrators tended to think "big picture," based on the answers they provided. These individuals were always thinking of the functionalities of the system as a whole rather than its small components. When asked if they thought they were a leader, this is a response I received: "Yes, I am a leader."

It appears that the administrators realize that they are not the single source of power and information; instead, they put their trust and faith in people who have been highly trained in their particular field to make the right decisions. Though some might argue that it is risky to put this level of trust and faith in another to make a decision that affects the whole organization, this ability is viewed as strong indicator of true leadership. True leadership is many times about enabling and trusting other individuals and providing them with all of the necessary components to succeed.

One of the administrators does supportive monitoring and guidance for enforcing the decisions taken.

Chief floor manager believed that a leader must have excellent communication skill, be a good trainer and also be able to provide counseling to others.

One of the floor manager had different opinions for different types of situations. The manager believed that what decision to take depends on a situation.

Another floor manager believed herself as a mediator between top management and bottom management.

Another floor manager believed strongly in team work and said that it is very effective and time saving.

Doctors also consider themselves as a leader. One of the doctors believes that team work is very important and each member of the team plays a vital role.

One of the doctors does not think himself as a leader, even he gets angry when some person disagrees with his decisions. His outcome is not valuable in collaborative work as he does not like to work in teams.

Another doctor also does not characterize himself as a leader but he likes to work in teams which make the work easier, convenient and time saving.

Nurses characterize themselves as a leader. One of the head nurse is very flexible in nature, if someone disagrees to her decisions she listens to the other persons view point and accepts it.

One of the nurses characterizes a good leader as the one who has discipline, self confidence, can take quicker decisions and respect others. She always tries to support others decision.

Another nurse characterizes a leader as the one who has good behavior, who is helpful, listens to everyone's problems and tries to solve it as soon as possible.

NURSE AS LEADER:

All forms of nursing leadership must result in excellent patient care and outcomes. Creating a warm, safe, and supportive organizational culture and work climate can be used to develop leaders. The roles and

responsibilities that shape the style of the nurse as a leader and the nurse manager can transport the nurse from bedside to boardroom easily, accurately, and with support and enthusiasm from the staff and leadership alike. In this study, we found affiliative leadership among nursing staff who works to create emotional bonds and also democratic leadership style in which the nurses builds consensus through participation.

ADMINISTRATOR AS LEADER:

One might expect a hospital administrator to be extremely power- and status-driven. The leadership development of a hospital administrator must start early in life. Typically, a person must have a long track record of successes to reach a hospital administrator position. In this study, we found administrator having coaching leadership that develops people for the future and also pacesetting leadership that expects and models excellence and self-direction.

FLOOR MANAGER AS LEADER:

While interacting with the floor managers I found coaching leadership in them which develops people for the future. If this style were summed up in one phrase, it would be "Try this." Floor managers wanted to help their teammates build lasting personal strengths that make them more successful overall. This style least effective when teammates are defiant and unwilling to change or learn, or if the leader lacks proficiency. Floor managers were also found having democratic leadership.

PHYSICIAN AS LEADER:

I noticed that physicians frequently speak in the plural. Physicians usually say "I" and "me," but rarely "we" and "us." This suggests that physicians do not have a collective identity. However, in a health care organization, imposing a decision without following the appropriate steps or gaining the acceptance of the whole group only ensures that the measure will be resisted. While physicians advocate for distributive justice when they are the ones giving the orders, they too demand justice when others give orders to them. Physicians tend to resist and teamwork. They are used to work under their own self-control, and partnership is a difficult quality to learn after many years of operating alone. Highly competitive physicians play a win-lose game. Physicians resist in engaging in collaborative behavior, or win-win negotiations, because collaboration requires trust and highly competitive physicians don't easily trust. In this study, we found physicians having coercive leadership which is most effective in times of crisis and also authoritative leadership which mobilizes the team towards a common vision and focuses on end goals.

Discussion

The study shows that all the professionals involved in the study keep their subordinates well informed about their decisions. This is similar to Gray's (1989) ⁶ work that framed successful collaborations as "negotiated inter organizational orders" that highlight the need for transparent leadership, adaptive and change-oriented management, and attention to effective processes that can lead to agreement (as much or more than programmatic goal orientation). This study also affirmed the validity of Wiltshire and Satterwhite's (1999)⁷ excellent ideographic study on collaboration, and Chen and Quiroz-Martínez's Diversity Network Project study (2004)⁸ that covered the traits of successful, diverse collaborations between environmental and social justice organizations. These two reports relied on interviews with many of the executive leaders; however, they did not explicitly focus on leadership styles for collaboration, but focused more on the traits of the collaborations themselves. This was found in this study also where the professionals at various executive positions answered that if their decisions are not well accepted by the subordinates they tend to implement it by involving higher authorities which indicated an authoritative leadership style of work.

Chrislip and Larson's (1994)⁹ principles of collaborative leadership described the leadership style of the interviewees in this study in the most comprehensive way. All of the principles that Chrislip and Lawson promoted were verified by the study participants. Those principles are reviewed below along with a few appropriate quotes from the interviewees that pertain to each of Chrislip and Lawson's principles. They are: Inspire commitment and action, Lead as peer problem solver, Build broad-based involvement, Sustain hope and participation, Servant Leadership and Leadership as a process. All these principles were reflected in the observations and interviewees response to the questionnaire.

The interviewees were mostly relationship rather than task motivated leaders, and operated successfully in situations in which they had low to moderate levels of control over their colleagues. Task-oriented leaders seemed to perform well in policy battles with extremely tight timeframes and well-defined outcomes – if they already had the relationships in place to address the issues. In most other longer-term contexts the interviewees used a relationship-oriented frame.

According to Bass (1990)¹⁰ and Yukl (2006)¹¹, transactional and transformational leadership are not and should not be mutually exclusive. Transformational behaviors include idealized influence (attributed), idealized influence (behavior), individualized considerations, inspirational motivation, and intellectual stimulation. Transactional behaviors include contingent reward, management by exception (active), and management by exception (passive).

In addition, it is important for each of these health care leaders to be engaged in practices of reflection. Bar-On defines self-reflection as “a process of exploring and evaluating our thoughts, feelings, and behavior.”¹² Through the process of self-reflection, health care leaders should be able to better access the needs of their organization on a more profound level of engagement. As mentioned earlier, Curtis et al recognized that leaders innovate, develop, inspire, challenge the status quo, and focus on a long-term vision.¹² From this research, the critical need for these health care leaders to engage in self-reflection to better understand themselves and have “thinking time” to set the direction for the future of their organization is evident. The health of each organization depends upon the health of the leader and his or her greater understanding of self.

Limitations

While this research is by no means a how-to manual, it does identify leadership styles and provides some key ideas on how to lead collaborations in the dynamic environment of hospital setting.

This research was clearly limited to leaders in the various aspects of interventions at hospital. Due to shortage of time the study could not be conducted on all the professionals involved. Hence, the results cannot be generalized to other sectors.

Recommendations

The data might also yield different results at another hospital; therefore, the data might not be a predictable indicator of future leadership and communication expectations and values.

Additionally, while this study matches specific health professions with selected leadership communication styles, it is important to remember that leaders must be adaptable and flexible. For example, hospital administrators in this study were most closely aligned with transformational leadership; however, it is critical for these leaders to also incorporate other leadership styles based on situational factors.

Future research needs to look at the core coursework of nurses, physicians, and administrators in educating them on the principles of leadership and effective communication. Future exploratory research could be conducted looking at the stereotypes applied to nurses, physicians, and administrators by subordinates or clients.

Conclusion

The practical implications of this research are important for all health care professionals. It is evident that physicians, nurses, and administrators must have an increased awareness of self and individual leadership style. Each individual having a better understanding of him or herself and how they are perceived from others may help the overall health of the organization. In addition, it is important for each of these health care leaders to be engaged in practices of reflection.

REFERENCES

1. Book on management development of Sikkim Manipal University.
2. Rojers R. (2006). Northouse PG. Leadership: a descriptive analysis of health care professional. Theory and Practice, 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks: Vol 34, pp 234-236
3. Dunkan K, (2009), Georgian College, improving skills and communications for supervisors and managers, JUST0010, VOI 44,pp 345-348
4. Madlok P E, (2009), link between communication style and competency. Lateness as a withdrawal behavior. Journal of Applied Psychology, Vol 66, pp 544-545.
5. Rebekah Rogers, School of Communication, East Carolina University, NC, USA, Leadership communication styles: a descriptive analysis of health care professionals, Journal of Healthcare Leadership.
6. Gray, B. (1989). Collaborating. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
7. Wiltshire, K. and Satterwhite, O. (1999). Common ground: Building collaborations for sustaining communities in the San Francisco Bay area. San Francisco, CA: San Francisco Foundation.
8. Chen, V. and Quiroz-Martinez, J. (2004). Powerful collaborations at the intersection of social justice and the environment: lessons learned from the diversity network project. San Francisco: The San Francisco Foundation and Wallace Alexander Gerbode Foundation.
9. Chrislip, D. & Larson, C. (1994). Collaborative leadership, San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
10. Bass, B. M. (1990). Bass & Stogdill's handbook of leadership: Theory, research, & managerial application (3rd ed.). New York, NY: Simon & Schuster, Inc.
11. Yukl, G. (2006). Leadership in organizations (6th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ Prentice Education.
12. Bar-On T. A meeting with clay: individual narratives, self-reflection, and action. In: Smith JK, Smith LF, Kaufman JC, editors. Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts [serial on the Internet]. 2007;1(4):225-236. Available from: <http://www.apa.org/pubs/journals/aca/index.aspx>. Accessed March 15, 2012.
13. Curtis AE, Vries JD, Sheerin FK. Developing leadership in nursing: exploring core factors. Br J Nurs. 2011;20(5):306-309.

Appendix

Interview questions ^[5]

Managers, doctors and nurses are often thought of by the public as "leaders;" would you characterize yourself as a leader? If so, what do you think makes you a good leader?

What happens if someone disagrees with your decisions?

How do you inform others about the decision? How do you enforce it?

How are you informed about others' decisions that affect you?

Do you ever have to do collaborative work in teams or groups? Can you provide an example of how you were particularly valuable to the outcome?

Is there anything else that you want to address about what we have discussed, e.g., your position, your role?